

USE OF LEXICAL UNITS IN THE TRANSLATION PROCESS

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Abstract. *When doing the exercise in this article, you will improve your ability to overcome difficulties in translation based on the development of skills in accurately printing and using the most frequent translation correspondences for introductory phrases. Fast translation of sentences from the text is done before the exercise and develops the ability to correctly and adequately choose the beginning of the sentence, as well as the ability to synthesize predictions. Students must memorize the equivalents of the selected word and phrases. After the plan is created, keywords are selected and the plan is filled with them. The teacher corrects the translation, gives a more suitable option, the translation of the text or phrase is necessarily suggested. Let's see how the issues of teaching translation are implemented in educational programs, as well as in teaching-methodical literature on translation and from the point of view of the studied problem, priority areas requiring further improvement can be distinguished. Training of translators is one of the main problems of translation science. Although the "educational paradigm" of consecutive translation, as mentioned above, emerged at the end of the 20th century, the growing diversity of professional fields challenged the idea of a standard training and pedagogical approach.*

Keywords: *translation, word, simultaneous translation, consecutive translation, translator, difference, question.*

The integration of Uzbekistan into the world community, the establishment of international relations of our republic with foreign countries in all spheres of economy and culture is increasing the demand for translation. The most important condition for the successful training of future translators is the improvement of the educational process, the development of the methodology, as well as the creative approach to the teaching of translation by activating the individual abilities of students. A curriculum is "a contract between instructors and their students, designed to answer students' questions about the course, as well as inform them of what will happen if the course does not meet their expectations". [1.] It is also "a means of expressing responsibility and obligation"[2]. Over time, the concept of the curriculum as a document has gained meaning, but, in fact, it is not mandatory.[3.]

Let's see how the issues of teaching translation are implemented in educational programs, as well as in teaching and methodological literature on translation. and highlight priority areas that require further improvement in terms of the problem being studied.

Undoubtedly, special attention should be paid to mastering a foreign language in the teaching of the KKT. The unified state educational standard for foreign languages of the continuing education system was approved by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2013. The main regulatory legal documents on the preparation of the state educational standard for foreign languages are: the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", "On the National Program of Personnel Training"; Decision PQ-1875 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further

improve the system of learning foreign languages". The state educational standard is based on a communicative-active, student-oriented, integrative and competence-based approach to teaching foreign languages.[4] According to TestDAF (Test deutsch als Fremdsprache - Try German as a foreign language), for the first time in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the levels of knowledge of foreign languages were adopted according to the following table. The effectiveness of TestDAF was evaluated by F.M. Rashidova in her dissertation research "Improving the conceptual-methodological foundations of the introduction of TestDAF to the continuous education system of Uzbekistan (on the example of the German language)": "Improving the language knowledge system, consistent implementation of TestDAF implies dialectical development. on the quality and efficiency of education". [5] 5120200 – State Educational Standard (DTS) (qualification requirements for the field of study) in the field of translation theory and practice (Romance-Germanic languages) for obtaining a bachelor's degree in education contains information on general requirements. They consist of general requirements for a bachelor's degree, current qualification requirements for a bachelor of education in the field of translation, requirements in the field of translation and personnel training, professional skills and organizational-management activities, as well as requirements in the field of scientific research. the work. It is worth noting that the requirements are not divided into types of translation - written and oral, but represent the set of skills necessary for graduates of the 5120200 - Theory and practice of translation (Romanian-German languages). The sub-section of requirements in the special field of ST talks about the implementation of simultaneous, visual, consecutive interpretation at international conferences.

We believe that RAP skills in senior (3-4) year students should include:

- to have systematic knowledge, to develop a worldview, to know the basics of humanitarian and socio-economic sciences, current issues of current directions and trends of state policy, to be able to independently analyze social problems and processes;
- to have a comprehensive understanding of the processes and events occurring in society and nature, to acquire knowledge about nature and society and to use them in modern life and professional activity;
- able to independently acquire new knowledge, work on it and organize scientific activity on a scientific basis;
- to know the theoretical foundations of translation, grammatical, lexical, phraseological, stylistic and pragmatic problems of translation, types of translation, to acquire lexical competence, to master the main methods of translation.

5120200 – The training plan for KKT on the specialty of translation theory and practice focuses on acquiring theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the field of consecutive translation; also plans to develop a rich vocabulary and basic knowledge, which are mandatory competencies of a serial translator.

Training of translators is one of the main problems of translation science. Although the "educational paradigm" of consecutive translation, as mentioned above, emerged at the end of the 20th century, the growing diversity of professional fields challenged the idea of a standard training and pedagogical approach. questioned.[6]

The goals of the program on the subject "Consecutive translation in German" are to form linguistic, communicative, discursive, technical and informational skills, knowledge of translation changes and skills of writing translation cursive, as well as acquiring the so-called knowledge. The main theoretical part of the program for upper-class students is designed in accordance with the

requirements for each level of ST education. In the sections of the program, "Introduction to consecutive translation from German", "Translation into another language and its importance", "Subsequent translation and its features", "Useful tips for improving translation skills", "Consequential translation from German" basic principles" are included. Uzbek (from German to Russian and vice versa)", "Methods of translating phraseological units in the implementation of oral translation" and others.

But it should be noted that, firstly, KKT is an activity that develops through practice and, therefore, practical training. Based on this, the curriculum for TS (educational standard) in the upper years (3-4) includes information and practice-oriented exercises, as they cover the basics of translation theory in the junior years of study. However, it should be noted that it is impossible to become a competent serial translator without a certain theoretical foundation. We believe that it is necessary to complete the theoretical part of the program.

Second, we noted that some universities (SamGIIA) have sections on ST in their TS curriculum, which may affect the training of consecutive interpreters. Obviously, these 2 translators are very close, and often translators work in both modes, but it is important to remember that each type of translation has its own necessary skills and rules. Based on this, we believe that ST-related topics should not be included in the PC curriculum.

As mentioned above, KKT focuses on the development of practical skills, and as a result, the practical part of the program is the most extensive. It contains exercises to develop speech, build vocabulary (stable phrases), improve translation skills and develop basic knowledge. There are also exercises for teaching memory and cursive writing, but they do not fully meet the requirements for developing memory and cursive writing skills in a serial translator. Therefore, it is necessary to develop this field of practice, because it is the basis of the work of a consecutive interpreter. Also, in the practical part, there are no exercises for the development of other psychophysiological data of a consecutive interpreter - breathing, volume and voice adjustment, clarity of speech, diction. These skills are essential for working in the ST field, as the interpreter often speaks directly to the audience, which requires him to speak loudly and clearly. It follows from this work situation of the consecutive interpreter that in practice, the interpreter must be in stressful situations, therefore, during the educational process, it is necessary to create conditions close to real conditions for students as often as possible. Students need to develop sensitivity, confidence and resilience to stress. Finally, the program does not include visualization and mental imagery exercises. It should be noted here that visualization is any method of creating images, diagrams or animations to convey a message, i.e. it is a way of presenting the obtained data in the form of visual images. We hypothesize that these exercises contribute to the development of memory in interpreters, so that it is easier for the interpreter to remember the received information, because he will be able to (a) remember it not in the form it was received.

In higher courses, this subject is designed for 4 academic semesters for 152 hours for 5th and 6th semesters and 88 hours for 7th and 8th semesters (UzSUM), 214 hours for 7th and 8th semesters (SamDChTI), "Next stage" science. translation (Sequential translation)". Hours are also allocated for independent work: 150 hours for the 3rd year, 176 hours for the 4th year (UzDUVL), 164 hours for the 4th year (SamGIYA). Internationally, the training of both translators and interpreters has greatly improved over the last century.[7] One of the biggest changes is the rapid increase in the number of translation and interpretation training institutions, due to the growing demand for systematic training of professionals. According to D. Kelly and A. Martin, by 2006,

universities in 63 countries around the world offered 380 programs to train translators, while in 1960 there were only 49 programs.[8] To date, the teaching-methodical complex and training programs for teaching PT in Russian and Uzbek language classes of higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan have been created on the basis of O. Mominov's "Textbook on further translation"[9]. It consists of an introduction in 3 languages, a theoretical section on the history of KKT, its characteristics, the influence of culture on KKT, as well as a shorthand translation. After that, the practical part of the textbook includes exercises for oral ST on various topics: business negotiations, briefings, interpreting at conferences, interpreting official speeches, interpreting accompanied by delegations (escort interpreting), interpreting within the framework of traditions, customs and national characteristics, translation of presentations, translation in embassies, translation within the framework of United Nations activities, as well as translation of the most frequently used expressions.

The textbook contains exercises and audio recordings for listening. There are phrases translated into Russian and Uzbek, as well as texts of public speeches for translation into German and Russian and Uzbek.

In our opinion, although this textbook avoids the traditional mechanistic and uniform presentation of the material, it still has a number of shortcomings and needs to be improved. It does not contain exercises for training memory, creating mental images, as well as interactive exercises and video materials, i.e. the textbook contains traditional exercises and tasks, but it requires additions from the teacher. Also, the authors E. Muratova and N. Makhmudova "German language for masters. Interesting topics". This textbook contains authentic texts and materials and exercises for translation that can be used to teach ST.[10]

Basically, in addition to using the textbook, teachers independently select practical material on a specific topic.

The results of the analysis of the study programs and textbooks and practical materials of the course "Practical translation (German language)" of the course "Consistent translation" showed that:

- training programs and textbooks do not contain exercises for teaching psychophysiological information, visualization and creating mental images, as well as exercises for teaching KKT in real translation conditions.

- the textbooks do not fully meet the competencies required for a ST special translator, they require special additions by the teacher (for this, teachers need to have experience as a translator).

- exercises are not structured and are mainly aimed at developing vocabulary and technical skills.

Thus, our analysis shows that the programs and CES in the studied area have the necessary elements, but require some modifications and additions to improve the training of RAP and the training of ST-specialist interpreters. Foreign language certificates serve as the main tool for improving the quality and efficiency of education. It consists of general requirements for the bachelor's degree, basic requirements for a bachelor of education in the field of translation, requirements in the field of translation and personnel training, professional skills and organizational-management activities, as well as requirements in the field of scientific research. It should be noted that the requirements are not divided into types of translation - written and oral. The theory and practice of translation refers to the set of skills necessary for graduates. The sub-

section of requirements in the field of professionalism mentions the implementation of simultaneous, visual, consecutive interpretation at international conferences.

When introducing lexical units, the methods of explaining, specifying and showing them in a sentence are used. The exercise is carried out as follows:[11] the student reads the text, guesses about its meaning, translates it if possible. The teacher corrects the translation, gives a more suitable option, [12] if the translation is difficult, gives an example of a synonym for using this text or phrase in a sentence. In short, the translation of the text or phrase is necessarily offered, because students have to memorize the equivalents and phrases of the chosen word. The exercise develops the skills of probabilistic forecasting at the level of words and phrases based on the acquisition of theoretical and practical linguistic knowledge, as well as knowledge of the subject of the report, helps to overcome psychological difficulties. Before viewing the report, students read the questions, which gives them an opportunity to reframe the main idea of the content of the report. [13]They receive an installation to see, to find answers to questions about the content of the report, which develops the skills of semantic perception of the message and the invention of vaguely perceived semantic blocks based on existing knowledge about the topic of the report. Students watch the report. In front of them there are supports in the form of text lists, phrases, specific vocabulary (proper names, names of days of the week and months) and questions to the text. After viewing the report for the first time, students should outline the report in addition to answering the questions. The questions serve as a basis. The text goes through the list of words and phrases from the first exercise to reveal the points of the plan. The exercise develops the ability to extract syntactic-semantic blocks and understand their meaning, based on the skill of selecting the most important parts from the point of view of semantics, and the skill of basic segmentation. With the help of this exercise, the ability to logically structure the text is developed, which is based on the performance of the skill of grasping syntactic structures and keeping them in memory for the fulfillment of grammatical obligations. After the first viewing, there will be a joint discussion, students will answer questions. During the review process, each student works independently, then each element is discussed and a shared decision is made. After the plan is created, keywords are selected and the plan is filled with them, which will serve as an aid for restating the report. The exercise is aimed at improving the skill of selecting semantically important fragments of the translation. In addition, during this exercise, the ability to logically structure the text is updated with the participation of the ability to acquire syntactic structures and save them for the fulfillment of grammatical obligations, the ability to repeat the content received from memory in different versions. Presentation of a message in a foreign language in the presence of the ability to retell a story with the help of a text, as well as retain the equivalents of translated structures in short-term memory, as well as translation skills under speech compression conditions and intensive memory based on the performance of the lexical skill of narrowing or logically expanding the meaning work is considered.[14] The exercise develops the ability to logically structure the text and develop the idea in translating the content of the report, as well as the ability to present the message in the translation based on the ability to preserve the equivalents of the message. Interpreter teachers attach special importance to this. The exercise consists of filling in the gaps in the text or phrases offered from the text of the TV report, based on drawing on existing knowledge and memorizing the content of the translation. It is believed that this exercise shows the level of knowledge of a foreign language (lexical, semantic and syntactic aspects), especially one of the main indicators of the formation of speech skills - the ability to predict the elements that will appear in a sequence in

the text. Such an exercise is useful for the development of both discursive and reflective skills in getting rid of psychological difficulties. The development of probability skills of words, phrases and sentences in close training is carried out on the basis of theoretical and practical language knowledge, knowledge of the topic of speech, and the presence of the formed skills of mastering speech. Uses the exercise to help students read and translate introductory phrases found in the text. This exercise is effective because often the difficulty in creating text is finding the beginning of the sentence.

In terms of purpose, the exercises are similar to the previous ones, but will focus on a different group of difficulties - translating specific texts and phrases from the report. In addition to developing the skills of accurately recording and using the most frequent translation correspondences, the ability to use lexical changes (modulation, generalization, concretization) is being improved.[15]

The exercises used in this area are aimed at developing the ability to apply different types of translation changes. Students are offered groups of phrases and sentences from the report, the adequate translation of which involves using the changes noted in the setting. First, students will practice using grammatical changes, and then they will practice using lexical changes in translation. Then the students are offered a list of lexical items that should be used in the construction of sentences. In the last 10-15 years, the main indicators of scientific activity have doubled. Acceleration of the development of science and scientific and technical information leads to rapid growth and frequent updating. The development of science according to the exponential law means its exponential growth. Therefore, the growth of scientific and technical information is considered as an avalanche. Every year, thousands of books and journals are published and thousands of dissertations are defended in the world. Modern telecommunication information systems are being used in order to ensure the speed of the increasing avalanche flow of information. The development of science is the sphere of activity of highly educated specialists. Therefore, the system of training of highly educated specialists should give their talented people the opportunity to master the modern flow of information, to develop the skills of individual and independent work in scientific research, to work creatively with scientific and technical information and educational scientific literature. . The avalanche development of modern science is ensured by the connection of two, three and more disciplines, and the emergence of new types of sciences. A new science born from connections of known disciplines means new directions, problems, topics and scientific issues. These issues should be solved by the talented graduates of the higher school. Therefore, a modern system of personnel training should develop unique and non-standard thinking skills in them, develop the skills of working on oneself with endurance and perseverance. The avalanche development of science and the corresponding growth of scientific and technical information leads to an increase in the speed of information transmission and processing, which is based on computing technology. It is impossible to imagine the use of modern information systems without individualization of education. Therefore, the higher school has been assigned the task of "Individualization of study, independent learning, and development and mastering of distance education system technologies and tools." The feature of scientific and technical progress is a sharp increase in the type of engineering solutions, rapid exchange of materials, technological processes, machine construction, an increase in the level of automation of control systems, and a reduction in the period of application of the results of scientific achievements to production. In order to prepare specialists who fully meet the increasing

requirements of the accelerating scientific and technical development in higher education, it is necessary to accelerate teaching, to use all the capabilities of the human body and its mind in education. It is necessary to accelerate teaching with new symbols. This requires the use of educational television, structuring and systematization of educational material, and computerization of teaching when providing information during the educational process. Every person from birth is considered a separate individualism, that is, everyone has his own mind and ability to learn. Based on this, the task of the modern education system should be focused on the development of individual human abilities. As noted, it is necessary to "accelerate education of students using new pedagogical and information technologies, modular system of training". The term "module training" is an international concept related to the module, which means a node consisting of interrelated elements that can function as one. In this sense, it is understood as the main tool of modular teaching, as a complete block of information.

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